

gap junction protein, alpha 3, 46kDa (connexin 46) (GJA3) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

shriprakash sinha

Independent Researcher; Orcid : 0000-0001-7027-5788

104-Madhurisha Heights Phase 1, Risali, Bhilai-490006, India

Abstract

Background : GJA3 belongs to the group of connexins, or gap junction proteins, that are a family of structurally related transmembrane proteins that assemble to form vertebrate gap junctions, which are different from the innexins, form gap junctions in invertebrates. They are essential for many physiological processes, such as proper embryonic development, the coordinated depolarization of cardiac muscle, and the conducted response in microvasculature. For these reasons, mutations in connexin-encoding genes can lead to functional and developmental abnormalities. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interations with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of GJA3, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way

*ML dicoveries of GJA3 synergy in Meningiomas

Email address: sinha.shriprakash@yandex.com (shriprakash sinha)

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for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: GJA3, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [4]). As of 2021, there

exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [5]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [6] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [7], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [8] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [9]. Finally, Cushing [10] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [13] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [11] and Pamir et al. [12]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. gap junction protein, alpha 3, 46kDa (connexin 46) (GJA3)

The channels that allow passage of small molecules between adjacent cells are made up of oligomeric proteins (connexins) that are encoded by a family of related genes. Connexin genes code for proteins that form cell-to-cell channels known as gap junctions. By the analysis of a panel of human-mouse somatic cell hybrids using rat cDNA probes, Willecke et al. [14] assigned the genes for the known connexins 26, 32, 43, and 46, to human chromosomes, 13, X, 6, and 13, respectively.

Hsieh et al. [15] mapped four functioning gap junction genes (i.e $\alpha 1$, $\beta 1$, $\beta 2$, and $\alpha 3$), to different sites on human chromosomes: GJA1 (connexin43) to 6p21.1-q24.1; GJB1 (connexin32) to Xcen-q22; GJB2 (connexin26) to 13; and GJA3 (connexin46) also to 13, probably near GJB2; by probing somatic cell hybrid DNA on Southern filters with rat or human cDNAs or human genomic fragments.

To determine the specific role of $\alpha 3$ connexin in vivo, Gong et al. [16] disrupted the $\alpha 3$ connexin gene (i.e Gap junction channel formed by $\alpha 3$ (Cx46)), in mice. They observed that although the absence of $\alpha 3$ connexin had no obvious influence on the early stages of lens formation and the differentiation of lens fibers, mice homozygous for the disrupted $\alpha 3$ gene developed nuclear cataracts that were associated with the proteolysis of crystallins.

Loci for autosomal dominant "zonular pulverulent" cataract have been mapped to chromosomes 1q (CZP1) and 13q (CZP3). Mackay et al. [17] reported genetic refinement of the CZP3 locus and identified the underlying mutations in the gene for GJA3 (or connexin46 Cx46). Their study identified GJA3 as the 6th member of the connexin gene family to be implicated in human disease, and highlighted the physiological importance of gap-junction communication in the development of a transparent eye lens.

Connexin $\alpha 1$ (Cx43 / GJA1) was previously shown to bind to the PDZ domain-containing protein ZO-1. Further, the similarity of the carboxyl termini of this connexin and the lens fiber connexins $\alpha 3$ (Cx46 / GJA3) and $\alpha 8$ (Cx50 / GJA8) suggested that these connexins may also interact with ZO-1. ZO-1 was shown to be highly expressed in mouse lenses. Benedetti and Kumar [18] demonstrated the colocalization of ZO-1 with (Cx46 / GJA3) and (Cx50 / GJA8) connexins in fiber cells, by immunofluorescence and fracture-labeling electron microscopy. However, they showed regional variations throughout the lens. Their results indicated that ZO-1 interacted with lens fiber connexins (Cx46 / GJA3) and (Cx50 / GJA8), similar to that previously described for (Cx43 / GJA1).

Burdon et al. [19] observed that a novel mutation in the Connexin 46 gene caused autosomal dominant congenital cataract with incomplete penetrance.

Congenital cataract (CC) is the leading cause of visual disability in children. In a four-generation Chinese family with congenital nuclear pulverulent and posterior polar cataracts, Yao et al. [20] detected a heterozygous c.5G>A transition in the second exon of GJA3, that resulted in the substitution of a highly conserved glycine with aspartic acid (p.G2D) at the N-terminus of the connexin46 (Cx46) protein. They observed that unlike wt Cx46, Cx46G2D mutant formed gap junction plaques inefficiently, that changed hemichannel permeability, and caused apoptosis.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.3. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries.

Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.4. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [21] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [22] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [22].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning

approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [23]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formating the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [24], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [21] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [21]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [25], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") •

use `source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R")`.

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. GJA3 related synergies

Note - GJA3 was found to be upregulated in Type C. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 258 2^{nd} order combinations of GJA3 were recorded.

3.1.1. FOXM1/WNT signaling target genes in Vasudevan et al. [3]

Meningioma is the most common primary intracranial tumor, but the molecular drivers of aggressive meningioma are incompletely understood. Using 280 human meningioma samples and RNA sequencing, immunohistochemistry, whole-exome sequencing, DNA methylation arrays, and targeted gene expression profiling, Vasudevan et al. [3] defined the molecular profile of aggressive meningioma. Their transcriptomic analyses identified FOXM1 as a key transcription factor for meningioma proliferation and a marker of poor clinical outcomes, while they discovered genomic and epigenomic factors associated with FOXM1 activation in aggressive meningiomas. Finally, they defined a FOXM1/WNT signaling axis in meningioma that was associated with a mitotic gene expression program, poor clinical outcomes, and proliferation of primary meningioma cells.

Vasudevan et al. [3] provide a set of FOXM1 target genes in meningioma and they also defined a FOXM1/WNT signaling axis in meningioma that was associated with a mitotic gene expression program, poor clinical outcomes, and proliferation of primary meningioma cells. Of these, CDC28 protein kinase regulatory subunit 2 (CKS2), TPX2 microtubule nucleation factor (TPX2), DNA topoisomerase II alpha (TOP2A), cyclin B2 (CCNB2), cell division cycle associated 5 (CDCA5), trophinin associated protein (TROAP), thymidine kinase 1 (TK1), BUB1 mitotic checkpoint serine/threonine kinase B (BUB1B), centromere protein F (CENPF), SPC25 component of NDC80 kinetochore complex (SPC25), kinesin family member 4A (KIF4A), NIMA related kinase 2 (NEK2), kinesin family member 18B (KIF18B), BRCA1 interacting DNA helicase 1 (BRIP1), DEP domain containing 1B (DEPDC1B) and Holliday junction recognition protein (HJURP), were found to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1].

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of GJA3 with these genes.

Table 1 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 2 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1. The table 1 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t GJA3. CKS2 - GJA3 shows high ranking of , 178 (laplace) , 217 (linear) , 146 (rbf) , 200 (jansen); TOP2A - GJA3 shows high ranking of , 210 (laplace) , 198 (linear) , 158 (rbf) , 209 (jansen); CCNB2 - GJA3 shows high ranking of , 252 (laplace) , 212 (linear) , 258 (rbf) , 89; TROAP - GJA3 shows high ranking of , 198 (laplace) , 230 (linear) , 141 (rbf) , 138; and TK1 - GJA3 shows high ranking of , 241 (laplace) , 161 (linear) , 249 (rbf) , 231 (jansen).

While, TPX2 - GJA3 shows low ranking of , 16 , 3 , 29 , 143; CDCA5 - GJA3 shows low ranking of , 108 , 249 , 161 , 99; BUB1B - GJA3 shows low ranking of ,

189 , 133 , 117 , 177; CENPF - GJA3 shows low ranking of , 27 , 32 , 26 , 157; SPC25 - GJA3 shows low ranking of , 130 , 232 , 97 , 202; KIF4A - GJA3 shows low ranking of , 3 , 23 , 20 , 71; NEK2 - GJA3 shows low ranking of , 1 , 36 , 33 , 169; KIF18B - GJA3 shows low ranking of , 190 , 132 , 94 , 42; BRIP1 - GJA3 shows low ranking of , 137 , 258 , 174 , 254; DEPDC1B - GJA3 shows low ranking of , 41 , 50 , 31 , 165; and HJURP - GJA3 shows low ranking of , 180 , 140 , 116 , 208.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS GJA3

RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T GJA3				
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
CKS2 - GJA3	178	217	146	200
TPX2 - GJA3	16	3	29	143
TOP2A - GJA3	210	198	158	209
CCNB2 - GJA3	252	212	258	89
CDCA5 - GJA3	108	249	161	99
TROAP - GJA3	198	230	141	138
TK1 - GJA3	241	161	249	231
BUB1B - GJA3	189	133	117	177
CENPF - GJA3	27	32	26	157
SPC25 - GJA3	130	232	97	202
KIF4A - GJA3	3	23	20	71
NEK2 - GJA3	1	36	33	169
KIF18B - GJA3	190	132	94	42
BRIP1 - GJA3	137	258	174	254
DEPDC1B - GJA3	41	50	31	165
HJURP - GJA3	180	140	116	208

Table 1: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between GJA3 VS Individual members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t GJA3 with GJA3 – > CKS2 / TOP2A / CCNB2 / TROAP / TK1.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t GJA3

CKS2	GJA3
TOP2A	GJA3
CCNB2	GJA3
TROAP	GJA3
TK1	GJA3

Table 2: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between GJA3 and Individual members.

3.1.2. GJA3 unknown combinations with high ranking

Along with the above known genes affected by GJA3, there are others genes that were upregulated and recorded in Patel et al. [1]. i document here, the 2nd order combinations with GJA3, which were assigned high rank by the machine learning based search engine. These high ranks point to the possible existence of synergy between the GJA3 and the genetic factors, that might not have been explored till now. Further, wet lab tests will confirm the veracity of these rankings.

Of these, endonuclease/exonuclease/phosphatase family domain containing 1 (EEDP1), Holliday junction recognition protein (HJURP), prostate transmembrane protein, androgen induced 1 (PMEPA1), hypoxia inducible factor 3 subunit alpha (HIF3A), H1.3 linker histone, cluster member (HIST1H1D), transmembrane O-mannosyltransferase targeting cadherins 4 (TMTC4), transmembrane protein 74B (TMEM74B), DNA topoisomerase II alpha (TOP2A), CD101 molecule (CD101), neuron navigator 1 (NAV1), trophinin associated protein (TROAP), BRCA1 interacting DNA helicase 1 (BRIP1), Rho guanine nucleotide exchange factor 39 (ARHGEF39), nucleolar and spindle associated protein 1 (NUSAP1), centrosomal protein 55 (CEP55), ADAM metallopeptidase with thrombospondin type 1 motif 17 (ADAMTS17), denticleless E3 ubiquitin protein ligase homolog (DTL), ankyrin repeat domain 31 (ANKRD31), synaptotagmin like 5 (SYTL5), pantothenate kinase 1 (PANK1), cyclin B2 (CCNB2), diacylglycerol kinase iota (DGKI), thymosin beta 15A (TMSB15A), solute carrier family 13 member 3 (SLC13A3), cell division cycle 25C (CDC25C), S100 calcium binding protein A1 (S100A1), plexin domain containing 1 (PLXDC1), tubulin epsilon and delta complex 2 (TEDC2), ribosomal protein L22 like 1 (RPL22L1), melanotransferrin (MELTF), growth differentiation factor 9 (GDF9), PTTG1 regulator of sister chromatid separation, securin (PTTG1), solute carrier family 29 member 4 (SLC29A4), G protein-coupled receptor 146 (GPR146), maternal embryonic leucine zipper kinase (MELK), spindle and kinetochore associated complex subunit 3 (SKA3), 3-hydroxyacyl-CoA dehydratase 1 (HACD1), cellular retinoic acid binding protein 1 (CRABP1), PCNA clamp associated factor (PCLAF), chromatin licensing and DNA replication factor 1

(CDT1), thymidine kinase 1 (TK1), PDZ binding kinase (PBK), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily A regulatory beta subunit 3 (KCNAB3), cyclin dependent kinase 1 (CDK1), progesterin and adipoQ receptor family member 8 (PAQR8), ribonucleotide reductase regulatory subunit M2 (RRM2), membrane associated ring-CH-type finger 3 (MARCH3), exonuclease 1 (EXO1), carbohydrate sulfotransferase 2 (CHST2), ubiquitin conjugating enzyme E2 C (UBE2C), zinc finger protein 114 (ZNF114), vomeronasal 1 receptor 1 (VN1R1), apolipoprotein L domain containing 1 (APOLD1), H2A clustered histone 6 (HIST1H2AC), IZUMO1 receptor, JUNO (IZUMO1R), ERCC excision repair 6 like, spindle assembly checkpoint helicase (ERCC6L), 3-hydroxyacyl-CoA dehydratase 4 (HACD4), FAM111 trypsin like peptidase B (FAM111B), X-ray repair cross complementing 2 (XRCC2), BLM RecQ like helicase (BLM), protocadherin gamma subfamily A, 1 (PCDHGA1), spire type actin nucleation factor 2 (SPIRE2), microRNA 635 (MIR635), tripartite motif containing 59 (TRIM59), reticulocalbin 1 pseudogene 2 (RCN1P2), VIM antisense RNA 1 (VIM-AS1), MIR181A1 host gene (MIR181A1HG), deleted in lymphocytic leukemia 2 (DLEU2), DARS1 antisense RNA 1 (DARS-AS1), NALCN antisense RNA 1 (NALCN-AS1), NADH:ubiquinone oxidoreductase subunit B1 pseudogene 2 (NDUFB1P2), thioredoxin domain containing 5 (TXNDC5), RRS1 divergent transcript (RRS1-AS1), dynein axonemal heavy chain 10 opposite strand (DNAH10OS) and phosphoglycerate mutase 1 pseudogene 8 (PGAM1P8), were found to be recorded as upregulated in data by Patel et al. [1]. Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of GJA3 with these genes.

Table 3 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 4 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 3. The table 3 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t GJA3.

One can also interpret the results of the table 3 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t GJA3 with GJA3 \rightarrow EEPD1 / HJURP / PMEPA1 / HIF3A / HIST1H1D / TMTC4 / TMEM74B / TOP2A / CD101 / NAV1 / TROAP / BRIP1 / ARHGEF39 / NUSAP1 / CEP55 / ADAMTS17 / DTL / ANKRD31 / SYTL5 / PANK1 / CCNB2 / DGKI / TMSB15A / SLC13A3 / CDC25C / S100A1 / PLXDC1 / TEDC2 / RPL22L1 / MELTF / GDF9 / PTTG1 / SLC29A4 / GPR146 / MELK / SKA3 / HACD1 / CRABP1 / PCLAF / CDT1 / TK1 / PBK / KCNAB3 / CDK1 / PAQR8 / RRM2 / MARCH3 / EXO1 / CHST2 / UBE2C / ZNF114 / VN1R1 / APOLD1 / HIST1H2AC / IZUMO1R / ERCC6L / HACD4 / FAM111B / XRCC2 / BLM / PCDHGA1 / SPIRE2 / MIR635 / TRIM59 / RCN1P2 / VIM-AS1 / MIR181A1HG / DLEU2 / DARS-AS1 / NALCN-AS1 / NDUFB1P2 / TXNDC5 / RRS1-AS1 / DNAH10O / PGAM1P8.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic GJA3 2^{nd} order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of GJA3-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

RANKING UNKNOWN INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS GJA3									
RANKING OF UNKNOWN INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T GJA3									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
EEPD1 - GJA3	227	233	114	170	HJURP - GJA3	180	140	116	208
PMEPA1 - GJA3	211	179	235	244	HIF3A - GJA3	193	170	208	127
HIST1H1D - GJA3	237	136	194	53	TMTC4 - GJA3	138	190	184	131
TMEM74B - GJA3	192	193	125	119	TOP2A - GJA3	210	198	158	209
CD101 - GJA3	206	174	201	210	NAV1 - GJA3	187	255	192	226
TROAP - GJA3	198	230	141	138	BRIP1 - GJA3	137	258	174	254
ARHGEF39 - GJA3	204	114	212	192	NUSAP1 - GJA3	199	100	166	227
CEP55 - GJA3	257	162	233	171	ADAMTS17 - GJA3	255	209	187	121
DTL - GJA3	202	221	196	47	ANKRD31 - GJA3	238	213	240	144
SYTL5 - GJA3	243	203	245	224	PANK1 - GJA3	209	201	173	94
CCNB2 - GJA3	252	212	258	89	DGKI - GJA3	179	110	232	221
TMSB15A - GJA3	197	240	225	228	SLC13A3 - GJA3	245	223	185	55
CDC25C - GJA3	153	156	226	246	S100A1 - GJA3	258	81	181	211
PLXDC1 - GJA3	256	224	89	185	TEDC2 - GJA3	247	185	222	247
RPL22L1 - GJA3	75	236	160	153	MELTF - GJA3	222	253	220	104
GDF9 - GJA3	218	226	213	229	PTTG1 - GJA3	143	200	214	187
SLC29A4 - GJA3	173	151	83	149	GPR146 - GJA3	230	178	163	212
MELK - GJA3	160	238	248	213	SKA3 - GJA3	154	194	151	118
HACD1 - GJA3	136	251	215	255	CRABP1 - GJA3	208	166	250	116
PCLAF - GJA3	145	219	239	222	CDT1 - GJA3	89	220	210	230
TK1 - GJA3	241	161	249	231	PBK - GJA3	214	208	224	214
KCNAB3 - GJA3	234	125	247	248	CDK1 - GJA3	216	218	207	172
PAQR8 - GJA3	249	228	167	232	RRM2 - GJA3	99	183	170	186
MARCH3 - GJA3	236	175	144	112	EXO1 - GJA3	169	91	243	173
CHST2 - GJA3	196	143	206	249	UBE2C - GJA3	150	117	205	178
ZNF114 - GJA3	228	243	129	193	VN1R1 - GJA3	221	241	95	223
APOLD1 - GJA3	186	211	84	194	HIST1H2AC - GJA3	172	121	179	159
IZUMO1R - GJA3	168	184	120	155	ERCC6L - GJA3	225	189	98	219
HACD4 - GJA3	253	167	190	100	FAM111B - GJA3	231	171	85	150
XRCC2 - GJA3	149	214	255	233	BLM - GJA3	201	172	176	250
PCDHGA1 - GJA3	147	229	172	195	SPIRE2 - GJA3	215	247	121	168
MIR635 - GJA3	124	256	191	180	TRIM59 - GJA3	250	187	246	257
RCN1P2 - GJA3	195	128	186	241	VIM-AS1 - GJA3	174	158	204	182
MIR181A1HG - GJA3	248	173	227	188	DLEU2 - GJA3	188	250	234	215
DARS-AS1 - GJA3	104	188	216	216	NALCN-AS1 - GJA3	213	168	221	95
NDUFB1P2 - GJA3	235	215	149	197	TXNDC5 - GJA3	200	177	193	236
RRS1-AS1 - GJA3	226	164	148	237	DNAH10OS - GJA3	91	202	254	201
PGAM1P8 - GJA3	217	254	138	184					

Table 3: 2nd order interaction ranking between GJA3 VS Individual members.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Unknown Individual members w.r.t GJA3	
EEPD1 / HJURP / PMEPA1 / HIF3A / HIST1H1D ...	
TMTC4 / TMEB74B / TOP2A / CD101 / NAV1 ...	
TROAP / BRIP1 / ARHGEF39 / NUSAP1 / CEP55 ...	
ADAMTS17 / DTL / ANKRD31 / SYTL5 / PANK1 ...	
CCNB2 / DGKI / TMSB15A / SLC13A3 / CDC25C ...	
S100A1 / PLXDC1 / TEDC2 / RPL22L1 / MELTF ...	
GDF9 / PTTG1 / SLC29A4 / GPR146 / MELK ...	
SKA3 / HACD1 / CRABP1 / PCLAF / CDT1 / TK1 ...	
PBK / KCNAB3 / CDK1 / PAQR8 / RRM2 / MARCH3 ...	
EXO1 / CHST2 / UBE2C / ZNF114 / VN1R1 / APOLD1 ...	
HIST1H2AC / IZUMO1R / ERCC6L / HACD4 / FAM111B ...	
XRCC2 / BLM / PCDHGA1 / SPIRE2 / MIR635 / TRIM59 ...	
RCN1P2 / VIM-AS1 / MIR181A1HG / DLEU2 / DARS-AS1 ...	
NALCN-AS1 / NDUFB1P2 / TXNDC5 / RRS1-AS1 / DNAH10OS ...	
PGAM1P8	GJA3

Table 4: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between GJA3 and Individual members.

Acknowledgements

Special thanks to Mrs. Rita Sinha and Mr. Prabhat Sinha for supporting the author financially, without which this work could not have been made possible.

Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

5. References

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